

ANALYSIS OF COVERT MONITORING OF USER ACTIVITIES IN COMPUTER NETWORKS

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Abstract: National security has gained vital importance due to increasing number of suspicious and terrorist events across the globe. Use of different subfields of information technology has also gained much attraction of researchers and practitioners to design systems which can detect main members which are actually responsible for such kind of events. In this paper, we present a novel method to predict key players from a covert network by applying a hybrid framework. The proposed system calculates certain centrality measures for each node in the network and then applies novel hybrid classifier for detection of key players. Our system also applies anomaly detection to predict any terrorist activity in order to help law enforcement agencies to destabilize the involved network. As a proof of concept, the proposed framework has been implemented and tested using different case studies including two publicly available datasets and one local network.

Keywords: Network Analysis, SNA, Open source, Hybrid, Cyber-security.

Introduction: From the data published in electronic and print media, it can be clearly concluded that all terrorist events are done by organized terrorist organizations. Members of such organizations cannot operate in isolation and they interact and collaborate with one another in order to coordinate such unlawful events. Law enforcement agencies have information of such members, their affiliations, and communication and other activities of such organizations which are under observation. Krebs introduced “prevention or prosecution”. According to him, the existing methods focus more on prosecution which is of course after the event has

occurred. Although there exist very efficient social network analysis (SNA) measures which can be used to find the key players of the identified network, which can be removed to destabilize the network, the thing which lacks is the alarm of the exact time at which those key players should be removed in order to prevent the event. A social network is a social arrangement made up of a set of social actors such as individuals or organizations and a complex set of the dyadic ties between these actors. The social network perspective provides a clear way of analyzing the structure of whole social entities. SNA is a mathematical method for “connecting the dots,” that is, to analyze nodes and their relationships. SNA allows us to map and measure complex, sometimes covert, human groups and organizations. SNA has been applied in a number of applications in order to explore several interesting features of different sort of social networks especially with the advancement in information and communication technology and availability of social networks in electronic forms. An important area in SNA is the key player detection. Key player is defined as the most important node in a social network. Centrality is a key theory in the study of social networks in order to study organizational and team behavior. Central individuals control information flow and decision making within a network. Along with key player detection, outlier detection is also important to predict any abnormal activity. Outlier detection deals with detection of patterns from data which do not match expected normal behavior. These anomalous patterns are often known as outliers, anomalies, discordant observations, and so forth in different application domains. Outlier detection is a well-researched area having an immense use in a wide range of applications like fraud detection, insurance, intrusion detection in cyber security, fault detection in security critical systems, military surveillance for enemy activities, and so on.

Materials: An open source software NodeXL which plugs in with Microsoft excel is used for testing of key player detection. For proper evaluation of proposed framework, we have used three case studies. The nodes in all three networks are labeled as key players and normal members. Table 1 shows the network specification for all three case studies on which the proposed system is evaluated.

Table 1

Network specification.

Case study	Nodes	Edges	Key players
I	79	402	8
II	62	150	19
III	30	114	9

The first case study is taken from titled as Noordin Muhammad network. This subset of the Noordin Top Terrorist Network was drawn primarily from “Terrorism in Indonesia: Noordin's Networks,” a 2006 publication of the International Crisis Group. It includes relational data on the 79 individuals listed in Appendix C of that publication. The data were initially coded by Naval Postgraduate School students as part of the course “Tracking and Disrupting Dark Networks” under the direction of Professor Sean Everton, Codirector of the CORE Lab, and Professor Nancy Roberts. CORE Lab Research Associate Dan Cunningham also reviewed and helped clean the data. The Noordin Muhammad network. The dataset for second case study was first compiled by Krebs consisting the tragic September 11 attackers network. The overall network consisted of 62 nodes and 150 edges containing all the attackers and their helpers who helped or coordinated in any way to organize the attacks. Muhammad Atta was the leader as confirmed by Ossama Bin Laden in a video tape. The actual 19 hijackers who got crashed are labeled. They are considered important because they are the actual implementers of the attack.

Methods: The proposed model is based on the two contributions discussed earlier. So, aim of the model is to achieve two main objectives; the first is to find the key players of the terrorist networks which already have been detected and the second is to continuously monitor the activities of such groups with the aim to alarm the situations when the probability of a terrorist event is high.

Results: The detailed quantitative and comparative analysis of proposed system is performed in this section. The performance of proposed system is measured using sensitivity (sen), specificity (spec), accuracy (acc), and area under receiver operating

characteristics (ROC) curves (AUC) as figures of merit. Sensitivity is true positive rate and specificity is true negative rate. These parameters are calculated using 1 and 2, respectively, as follows: Sensitivity= $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$, (1) Specificity= $\frac{TN}{TN+FP}$, (2) Accuracy= $\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$,

i. T_P are true positive mean numbers of key players which are identified correctly;

ii. T_N are true negative mean numbers of normal members of network which are identified correctly;

iii. F_P are false positive mean numbers of normal members of network which are wrongly identified as key players;

iv. F_N are false negative mean numbers of key players which are wrongly identified as normal members of network.

The modeling of classifiers has been done using randomly selected 70% of data as training and remaining 30% data as testing. The experiments are repeated 10 times and their average results are given. Table 1 shows the results of proposed framework for key player detection on all three networks given in case studies.

Statistical performance evaluation of proposed framework for key player detection.

Case study	sen	spec	acc	AUC
I	93.69	89.71	91.52	0.91
II	89.31	87.03	88.73	0.86
III	95.03	96.42	95.91	0.93

The statistical analysis of proposed system is done with the help of ROC curves which are plots of sensitivity versus 1-specificity. This analysis is done for performance evaluation of proposed hybrid classifier (HC). The proposed hybrid classifier is compared with individual kNN, GMM, and SVM classifiers. The hybrid classifier is also compared with the existing well-established classifier ensemble methods such as AdaBoost, bagging, and random subspace methods (RSM). Table 2 shows the comparison of all these in terms of accuracy for key player detection.

Table 2

Comparison of hybrid classifier with existing ensemble methods.

Methods	Case study-I	Case study-II	Case study-III
KNN	84.35	80.09	81.32
GMM	87.72	84.38	87.50
SVM	88.03	81.25	93.75
AdaBoost	82.15	80.41	89.47
Bagging	86.78	81.57	90.72
RSM	86.13	82.61	87.03
Proposed hybrid classifier	91.52	88.73	95.91

The third case study which is based on the local network is also used to evaluate anomaly detection component of proposed system. A campus In/Out system was used to monitor the In/Out activities of the group members. Applying the proposed outlier detection strategy, the group was captured right at the moment when they were ready to attack. Set of attributes consisting of the hour of day of in and out times was extracted from the dataset and outlier detection was applied.

Conclusion: National security has attracted a number of researchers due to tragic events of terrorism across the globe especially from the field of information and communication technologies. This is because of the fact that, in order to carry out terrorist events, very extensive collaboration between terrorists can be observed including use of latest communication technologies. This opens antiterrorist activities research on the data collected from detected suspicious individuals. Application of social network analysis has also become a very active area of research due to the above mentioned fact. In this paper, we have proposed a new framework for combating terrorism which consists of key player detection part which is from social network analysis and an event predictor part which has its base from outlier detection. For key player detection, in order to utilize existing most effective measures of key player detection, a novel hybrid classifier based system has been

proposed which detected key players from given data. The second and important contribution is the prediction of any suspicious activity by monitoring the data of any network and identifying something abnormal by using time series analysis along with nearest neighbor analysis. The proposed framework has been tested using three case studies and number of statistical measures. The results taken clearly prove the validity and correctness of proposed framework. A new study from actual local event is taken and proposed system is tested on that as well. Along with proposed framework for key player detection, we have also tested a voting based method which takes care of all four centrality measures to detect the top k key players of the terrorist network. Here, k is equal to the total number of key players present in a network which is under study. A node is considered as key player of three out of four centrality measures declared it as key player. This idea detected key players with accuracies of and 79%, 65%, and 83.33% for all three case studies, respectively. The proposed framework achieved accuracies of 91.52%, 88.73, and 95.91% for the same case studies, respectively. The results showed the validity of our framework and it can be used for detection of key players for any suspicious network along with detection of any abnormal activity.

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